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FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A DRIVER OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: REGIONAL DISPARITIES AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The article examines the contribution of family-run businesses to employment generation in Uzbekistan’s tourism sector and identifies significant regional differences in their distribution. Based on official statistics for 2016–2025, the analysis demonstrates that tourism employment increased from 170.9 thousand to 290.6 thousand people, while exports of tourism services per capita rose tenfold to 122.2 US dollars. At the same time, this indicator remains five to seven times lower than the corresponding levels of Kazakhstan and the Russian Federation, indicating considerable opportunities for further growth. A comparative regional analysis of the shares of families and family enterprises highlights leading regions (Samarkand, Khorezm, Navoi, and Bukhara) as well as regions with additional development potential (Andijan, Namangan, Syrdarya, Tashkent region, and Tashkent city). A three-channel institutional mechanism comprising wage employment, entrepreneurial employment, and self-employment, supported by microcredit, training, and land allocation, is presented in a hierarchical framework. Based on the findings, targeted recommendations aimed at enhancing employment opportunities and strengthening family entrepreneurship across the regions are proposed.

Keywords: family entrepreneurship; tourism employment; self-employment; regional differences; household; institutional mechanism; Uzbekistan.

Аннотация. В статье исследуется вклад семейного бизнеса в обеспечение занятости в сфере туризма Узбекистана и выявляются существенные региональные различия в его развитии. На основе официальной статистики за 2016–2025 годы показано, что занятость в туризме увеличилась со 170,9 тыс. до 290,6 тыс. человек, а экспорт туристических услуг на душу населения вырос в десять раз и достиг 122,2 доллара США. Вместе с тем данный показатель остается в пять–семь раз ниже уровня Казахстана и Российской Федерации, что свидетельствует о наличии значительных возможностей для дальнейшего развития. Сравнительный анализ долей семей и семейных предприятий позволил выделить регионы-лидеры (Самаркандская, Хорезмская, Навоийская и Бухарская области), а также регионы, обладающие дополнительным потенциалом роста (Андижанская, Наманганская, Сырдарьинская, Ташкентская области и город Ташкент). Представлен трехканальный институциональный механизм обеспечения занятости, включающий наемную занятость, предпринимательскую деятельность и самозанятость, а также сформулированы адресные рекомендации по дальнейшему развитию семейного предпринимательства и повышению занятости населения.

Ключевые слова: семейное предпринимательство; занятость в туризме; самозанятость; региональные различия; домохозяйство; институциональный механизм; Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

Employment remains one of the most important socio-economic issues for labour-abundant transition economies. In Uzbekistan, more than half a million young people enter the working-age population each year, while the economy creates approximately 350–400 thousand new jobs. This indicates the need to expand effective and sustainable employment opportunities [1]. Traditional channels of job creation in state organisations and large enterprises cannot fully absorb this growing labour supply on their own; therefore, entrepreneurship, particularly its most accessible form — family business — is becoming increasingly important.

Tourism provides a particularly favourable environment for the development of family entrepreneurship. The sector’s services — accommodation, catering, guiding, handicrafts, and related activities — can often be organised within households by using residential premises, household plots, and inherited skills, with relatively low capital requirements and a short payback period [2]. Recognising this potential, the state has integrated

family entrepreneurship into employment policy through the “Every Family is an Entrepreneur” programme launched in 2018 [3] and through the strengthening of the mahalla institution [4]. Practical initiatives, such as the restoration of 576 households and the creation of 1,500 permanent jobs in the Hastimom mahalla of Tashkent, as well as the development of a gastronomic tourism street in Mirzo Ulugbek district, demonstrate the potential of this model at the neighbourhood level.

At the same time, the realisation of this potential differs across the country's regions, while the demographic basis of family business — the number, size, and structure of families — also varies from one territory to another. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to assess the contribution of family entrepreneurship to employment in tourism, to evaluate regional differences in its development in relation to the distribution of families, and to substantiate an institutional mechanism for expanding employment opportunities and reducing regional disparities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The employment dimension of tourism has long attracted the attention of researchers studying developing and transition economies. Szivas and Riley documented the role of tourism as a labour “refuge” during periods of economic transition, noting its capacity to absorb workers moving from restructuring industries [5]. Liu and Wall argued that tourism employment planning in developing countries should go beyond macro-level projections and focus more on human resource development at the destination level [6]. Baum, in turn, highlighted the need for a more comprehensive assessment of human resources in the tourism sector [7].

The family business strand of tourism research, developed by Getz and Carlsen, established that family-run ventures dominate the micro-scale of tourism supply and often combine economic objectives with lifestyle-oriented goals [8]. Lashley and Rowson, in their study of small hotels, demonstrated how the household and the firm can function as a single economic unit [9]. The theoretical basis for considering the family as a productive unit can be traced back to Becker's economic theory of the family [10]. Community participation approaches, particularly Tosun's analysis of local involvement in tourism development, emphasise that institutional support is essential to ensure that tourism benefits reach resident households [11]. Similarly, Sharpley's study of rural tourism diversification underlines the dependence of household-based tourism ventures on infrastructure development and policy support [12].

In the national literature, Pardayev, Tukhliev and Ostonov define family entrepreneurship in tourism as an activity based on family ownership and the intra-family distribution of income, aimed at meeting social and economic needs through the provision of tourism services [13]. However, the regional dimension, particularly the relationship between the territorial concentration of families and the emergence of family enterprises, has not yet been systematically examined using recent statistical data. This article seeks to address this research gap.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is based on official data from the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Tourism Committee, and the international statistical portal Knoema for 2016–2025 [14]. The analytical strategy combines several methodological approaches: (i) dynamic analysis of tourism employment and exports of tourism services in both absolute and per capita terms, with international benchmarking against Kazakhstan and the Russian Federation; (ii) structural analysis of the demographic base, including the number of families, average family size, and the territorial distribution of family enterprises across the fourteen administrative regions; (iii) comparative coefficient analysis, in which each region's share in the national stock of family enterprises is compared with its share in the national number of families, producing a simple localisation indicator of entrepreneurial activity; and (iv) institutional analysis of support mechanisms embedded in national programmes and organised through hierarchical modelling. Throughout the study, methods of comparison, grouping, analysis and synthesis, as well as graphical visualisation, are applied.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Tourism has become one of the fastest-growing sources of employment in the national economy. Between 2016 and 2024, the number of people employed in the sector increased from 170.9 thousand to 290.6 thousand, representing an additional 119.7 thousand jobs, or a 70 per cent increase (Figure 1a). Demand-side indicators grew even more rapidly: exports of tourism services rose from 422.1 million US dollars in 2021 to 4,588.1 million US dollars in 2025, increasing per capita exports from 12.2 to 122.2 US dollars (Figure 1b, Table 1).

Table 1
Resident population and exports of tourist services of Uzbekistan, 2021–2025¹

Indicator	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2025 to 2021, %
Resident population, thousand people	34,558.9	35,271.3	36,024.9	36,799.8	37,543.2	108.6
Exports of tourist services, mln USD	422.1	1,610.1	2,143.5	3,500.0	4,588.1	1,087.1
Tourist services exports per capita, USD	12.2	45.7	59.5	95.1	122.2	1,001.7

Figure 1. Employment in the tourism sector (a) and per-capita exports of tourist services (b) in Uzbekistan²

A comparison with neighbouring economies highlights further opportunities for growth: per capita exports of tourism services are approximately 612 US dollars in Kazakhstan and 860 US dollars in the Russian Federation, which is five and seven times higher than the level recorded in Uzbekistan, respectively [14]. This difference should be interpreted not as a shortcoming, but as an indicator of significant growth potential and additional employment opportunities that the tourism sector can generate in the future.

The demographic foundation of family entrepreneurship is broad and diverse. As of 1 January 2024, the republic had 9,729,961 families. Their territorial distribution, together with the average family size, is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2
Number of families, their share and average family size by region of Uzbekistan³

No.	Region	Number of families, units	Share, %	Average persons per family
1	Republic of Karakalpakstan	473,142	4.89	4.19
2	Andijan region	893,378	9.18	3.74
3	Bukhara region	570,033	5.85	3.54
4	Jizzakh region	343,977	3.53	4.31
5	Kashkadarya region	847,530	8.72	4.13

1 author's development

2 author's development

3 author's development

No.	Region	Number of families, units	Share, %	Average persons per family
6	Navoi region	297,933	3.07	3.56
7	Namangan region	790,641	8.13	3.81
8	Samarkand region	1,012,500	10.41	4.09
9	Surkhandarya region	695,853	7.15	4.06
10	Syrdarya region	237,352	2.44	3.80
11	Tashkent region	904,414	9.29	3.32
12	Fergana region	1,124,208	11.55	3.55
13	Khorezm region	557,669	5.73	3.40
14	Tashkent city	981,331	10.07	3.03
	Republic, total	9,729,961	100.0	3.72

The largest shares of families are concentrated in Fergana (11.55 per cent), Samarkand (10.41 per cent), Tashkent city (10.07 per cent), Tashkent region (9.29 per cent), and Andijan (9.18 per cent). Average family size ranges from 3.03 persons in Tashkent city to 4.31 persons in Jizzakh. Larger families are generally associated with predominantly rural regions, which are favourable settings for household-based tourism services such as guest houses, home dining, and craft workshops.

Against this demographic background, the geography of family enterprises demonstrates notable regional differentiation. Of the 47,813 family enterprises registered nationwide, Samarkand region accounts for 17.71 per cent, while its share in the country's total number of families is 10.41 per cent, resulting in a localisation ratio of 1.7. Khorezm, with 10.20 per cent of enterprises against 5.73 per cent of families, and Navoi, with 7.72 per cent against 3.07 per cent, demonstrate even stronger relative specialisation. Bukhara also exceeds parity, as shown in Table 3 and Figure 2. At the same time, Andijan (3.44 per cent of enterprises against 9.18 per cent of families), Namangan (2.26 per cent against 8.13 per cent), Syrdarya (0.51 per cent against 2.44 per cent), Tashkent region (8.35 per cent against 9.29 per cent), and Tashkent city (6.03 per cent against 10.07 per cent) possess additional opportunities to further expand family entrepreneurship in line with their demographic potential (Table 3).

Table 3
Territorial structure of family enterprises in Uzbekistan⁴

No.	Region	Family enterprises, units	Share of family enterprises, %	Share of families, %
1	Republic of Karakalpakstan	1,996	4.17	4.89
2	Andijan region	1,645	3.44	9.18
3	Bukhara region	2,987	6.25	5.85
4	Jizzakh region	1,734	3.63	3.53
5	Kashkadarya region	4,642	9.71	8.72
6	Navoi region	3,690	7.72	3.07
7	Namangan region	1,082	2.26	8.13
8	Samarkand region	8,477	17.71	10.41
9	Surkhandarya region	4,302	9.00	7.15
10	Syrdarya region	246	0.51	2.44
11	Tashkent region	3,990	8.35	9.29
12	Fergana region	5,261	11.00	11.55
13	Khorezm region	4,878	10.20	5.73
14	Tashkent city	2,883	6.03	10.07
	Republic, total	47,813	100.0	100.0

⁴ author's development

Figure 2. Shares of family enterprises and of families by region of Uzbekistan, per cent⁵

The pattern allows for a clear interpretation. The leading regions combine rich cultural heritage resources (Samarkand, Khiva in Khorezm, and Bukhara) with established traditions of hospitality and crafts. As a result, households in these regions have relatively direct and visible pathways for transforming family resources into tourism-related income. In regions with additional development potential, the main issue is not the limited number of families — indeed, the Fergana Valley regions are among the most family-rich territories in the country — but the need to strengthen intermediary mechanisms. These include destination marketing, the expansion of tourist flows, and the wider dissemination of support instruments available under national programmes.

These instruments are systematised in Figure 3, which presents the employment mechanism in a hierarchical form (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Hierarchical model of the institutional mechanism for ensuring employment through family entrepreneurship in tourism⁶

5 author's development

6 author's development

At the upper level, employment through family entrepreneurship in tourism develops through three channels: wage employment in state organisations, employment in entrepreneurial entities, and self-employment in household-based services. The middle tier includes the support instruments provided under the “Every Family is an Entrepreneur” programme: preferential microcredits and financial assistance; entrepreneurial skills training with mentoring through mini-clusters, where experienced entrepreneurs support newly starting families; and the allocation of unused land plots and market infrastructure facilities to newly established family businesses [3]. The base of the hierarchy reflects the expected outcomes: household income growth, new job creation, the formalisation of informal activity, and more balanced regional development. Self-employment deserves particular attention in tourism, as it is based on personal satisfaction, independence, full appropriation of profit, employment security, and social standing — motivations that naturally align with guest house management, home gastronomy, and craft production.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

First, tourism has confirmed its capacity as an important driver of employment, as demonstrated by a 70 per cent increase in sectoral employment during 2016–2024 and a tenfold rise in per capita exports of tourism services during 2021–2025. At the same time, the per capita benchmark of 122.2 US dollars, which remains five to seven times lower than the corresponding indicators of Kazakhstan and the Russian Federation, points to considerable opportunities for further employment growth. In this context, family entrepreneurship represents one of the most direct and accessible ways to mobilise this potential.

Second, regional differences in the development of family business are shaped not only by demographic factors, but also by institutional conditions and destination assets. Priority attention should be given to Andijan, Namangan, Syrdarya and Tashkent regions, as well as Tashkent city, where the share of family enterprises is lower than the share of families. In these territories, family enterprises should be developed with clear reference to domestic and inbound tourism demand, including agritourism and gastronomy in the Fergana Valley, as well as transit and event tourism around the capital. This would enable newly established enterprises to enter a sustainable growth trajectory even under conditions of limited resources.

Third, the monitoring of household welfare should take family size into account, since similar income levels may produce different per capita welfare outcomes in families of three and families of six. Larger rural families are among those for whom supplementary tourism income generated from household plots is particularly accessible. Therefore, training such families to transform their gardens, kitchens and craft skills into tourism services can serve as a low-cost employment measure with a multiplier effect.

Fourth, the three-channel institutional mechanism — wage employment, entrepreneurial employment and self-employment, supported by microcredit, mentoring through mini-clusters and land allocation — should be implemented with regional differentiation. Resources should be concentrated in areas where the gap between family potential and enterprise creation remains the widest. The implementation of these recommendations would contribute to the employment and welfare objectives of the “Uzbekistan – 2030” development strategy by supporting job creation with a multiplier effect.

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